

31st International Symposium on Lepton Photon Interactions at High Energies

Km Baseline Neutrino Experiments

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On behalf of the JUNO collaboration

17-21 July 2023

Abstract

Observations from various neutrino sources at different baselines are consistent with the three neutrino oscillation framework. Km baseline neutrino experiments provide excellent opportunities for the measurements of reactor antineutrino oscillation. At 2 km baseline, Daya Bay, RENO and Double Chooz achieved the world-leading precision of θ_{13} and Δm_{32}^2 . At 52.5 km, JUNO experiment is under construction and its primary goal is to determine the neutrino mass ordering and improve the current precision of θ_{12} , Δm_{32}^2 and Δm_{21}^2 by one order of magnitude. This proceedings focus on the latest progresses on the JUNO detector and physics. A brief overview of Daya Bay, RENO and Double Chooz experiments on the measurements of $\sin^2 2\theta_{13}$ are presented.

1 Introduction

The discovery of the neutrino oscillation [1, 2] is regarded as one of the most compelling evidences for new physics beyond the Standard Model of particle physics. The standard three-flavor neutrino oscillation pattern is well established after the observation of the neutrino oscillation in solar, atmospheric, accelerator and reactor neutrino experiments. Three neutrino mixing angles, θ_{12} , θ_{13} , and θ_{23} , and two independent neutrino mass splittings, $|\Delta m_{31}^2|$ (or $|\Delta m_{32}^2|$ and Δm_{21}^2 , defined as $\Delta m_{ij}^2 = m_j^2 - m_i^2$ ($i, j = 1, 2, 3, i > j$)), were measured with precisions at a level of few percents. However, the neutrino mass ordering (NMO) is still unknown. The NMO has only two possibilities: the normal ordering (NO, $m_1 < m_3$) and the inverted ordering (IO, $m_1 > m_3$). Determining NMO is one of the major goals for future neutrino oscillation experiments.

The km baseline neutrino experiment is a promising observatory for the reactor antineutrino oscillations. The reactor antineutrino survival probability in vacuum can be written as

$$P_{\bar{\nu}_e \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e} = 1 - \sin^2 2\theta_{13} (\cos^2 \theta_{12} \sin^2 \Delta_{31} + \sin^2 \theta_{12} \sin^2 \Delta_{32}) - \cos^4 \theta_{13} \sin^2 2\theta_{12} \sin^2 \Delta_{21}, \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta_{ij} = \Delta m_{ij}^2 L / (4E)$, in which L is the baseline and E is the antineutrino energy. At around 2 km, Daya Bay [3], RENO [4] and Double Chooz [5] achieved the world-leading measurements of θ_{13} . Thanks to a large value of $\sin^2 2\theta_{13}$, JUNO is able to simultaneously measure oscillations driven by small mass splitting (Δm_{21}^2) and large mass splitting (Δm_{31}^2 and Δm_{32}^2) at a baseline of 52.5 km. The antineutrino energy spectra with and without oscillation is shown in Fig. 1. The

Figure 1: JUNO reactor antineutrino energy spectra without (black) and with (grey, blue and red) the neutrino oscillation. The spectra are convoluted with the inverse beta decay cross-section with 6 years of data-taking. The grey dashed curve shows the spectrum by assuming $\theta_{13} = 0$ in Eq. 1, whereas the blue and red curves are obtained using the full oscillation probability for the normal and inverted mass orderings, respectively.

small oscillation peaks modulated by $\sin^2 2\theta_{13}$ in the oscillated antineutrino spectrum contain the NMO information. Precise measurement of the oscillated reactor antineutrino spectrum is a key to determine the NMO. This requires a 20 kt liquid scintillator detector with an unprecedented energy resolution of $\sigma_E/E = 3\%/\sqrt{E_{\text{vis}}}$, with E_{vis} being the visible energy in the detector in MeV.

The remainder of this proceedings is organised as follows. In Section 2, we introduce the latest JUNO detector progresses. In Section 3, the JUNO physics potentials on the is discussed. In Section 2. a brief overview of Daya Bay, RENO, and Double Chooz is presented. Section 5 is devoted to the summary.

2 JUNO detector

The JUNO experiment is located at Kaiping City, Guangdong Province, south China with baselines ranging from 52.11 km to 52.82 km from 2 Taishan reactor cores and 6 Yangjiang reactor cores. The civil construction of the underground laboratory is almost completed and the JUNO detector is under construction since 2021. The 650 m rock overburden suppresses the cosmic-ray muon flux to $4.1 \times 10^{-3}/(\text{s} \cdot \text{m}^2)$.

The JUNO detector consists of a Central Detector (CD), a water Cherenkov detector and a Top Tracker. A schematic view of the JUNO detector is shown in Fig. 2. The CD is a 20 kt liquid scintillator detector with a designed energy resolution better than $\sigma_E/E = 3\%/\sqrt{E_{\text{vis}}}$. The liquid scintillator target is contained in a 12-cm thick acrylic sphere with a 35.4 m inner diameter. The acrylic vessel is supported by a stainless steel structure via Connecting Bars. The stainless steel structure is instrumented by 17,612 20-inch high quantum efficiency PMTs, referred to as LPMTs, and 25,600 3-inch PMTs, referred to as SPMTs, yielding an integral 77.9 % photo-cathode coverage. An ultra-pure water buffer with a thickness of ~ 1.5 m fills the gap between the acrylic vessel and the stainless steel structure. The light yield at the detector center is expected to be 1665 photoelectrons (PEs) per MeV for a neutron capture on hydrogen signal based on the simulation. The CD is immersed in ultra-pure water Cherenkov detector instrumented with PMTs that serves as an active veto for cosmic-ray muons with an efficiency $\geq 99.5\%$ and as a passive shield against external radioactivity and neutrons from cosmic rays. The muon veto system is supplemented with an external muon tracker consisting of three layers of plastic scintillator repurposed from the OPERA experiment located at the top. This system covers about 60% of the surface above the water pool. For more information about the JUNO detector, please refer to Ref. [6].

In July 2023, the stainless steel structure was almost completed providing supports of the load of acrylic vessel, liquid scintillator, PMTs, front-end electronics, etc.. Half of the 265 acrylic panels have been assembled to create the acrylic vessel extending from the top to the equator. More than 5000 LPMTs and SPMTs have been installed on the stainless steel structure. The production and purification plants for the 20 kt liquid scintillator has been constructed distributed on surface and in underground laboratory. The detector construction is expected to be completed in 2024.

3 JUNO physics

As a multiple-purpose detector, JUNO is sensitive to various neutrino sources beyond the reactor antineutrinos. The expected potentials of corresponding physics potentials is reviewed in Ref. [6]. The expected neutrino signal rates and major background sources are summarized in Tab. 1. Only the NMO determination requires a 3% energy resolution. The $|\Delta m_{32}^2|$ measurement benefits moderately from a high energy resolution. All other studies are not sensitive to the energy resolution. Solar neutrino studies require a U/Th radiopurity of the LS of 1×10^{-17} g/g. Reactor and Geoneutrino studies require 1×10^{-15} g/g and other studies are not sensitive.

An updated estimate of JUNO's sensitivity to NMO is performed in a joint analysis of JUNO and Taishan Antineutrino Observatory (TAO) which provides a constraint of the reactor antineutrino spectral shape. This NMO is determined by studying the fine interference pattern caused by quasi-vacuum oscillations in the oscillated spectrum of reactor antineutrinos shown in Fig. 1 and is completely independent of CP violating phase and neutrino mixing angle θ_{23} . The

Figure 2: Schematic view of the JUNO detector. An acrylic vessel containing 20 kt of liquid scintillator is immersed in water and surrounded by 17,612 large (20-inch) and 25,600 small (3-inch) inward-facing PMTs. This Central Detector is optically decoupled from a surrounding water pool instrumented with 2,400 20-inch PMTs providing shielding and cosmic-ray muon tagging. A Top Tracker system provides precision tracking of cosmic-ray muons entering the Central Detector.

Research	Expected signal	Energy region	Major backgrounds
Reactor antineutrino	60 IBDs/day	0–12 MeV	Radioactivity, cosmic muon
Supernova burst	5000 IBDs at 10 kpc 2300 elastic scattering	0–80 MeV	Negligible
DSNB (w/o PSD)	2–4 IBDs/year	10–40 MeV	Atmospheric ν
Solar neutrino	hundreds per year for ^8B	0–16 MeV	Radioactivity
Atmospheric neutrino	hundreds per year	0.1–100 GeV	Negligible
Geoneutrino	~ 400 per year	0–3 MeV	Reactor ν

Table 1: Summary of detectable neutrino signals in the JUNO experiment and the expected signal rates and major background sources.

sensitivity is obtained through a joint analysis of JUNO and TAO experiments utilizing the best available knowledge to date including the location and overburden of the JUNO experimental site, the nuclear reactors in the vicinity and beyond, the detector responses of both the JUNO and TAO detectors, the expected event rates and spectra of signal and backgrounds, and the systematic uncertainties of the analysis inputs. It is found that a 3σ median sensitivity can be reached to reject the wrong mass ordering hypothesis with an exposure of 6 years \times 26.6 GW thermal power. The sensitivity versus the data taking time is shown in Fig. 3.

The precision of the oscillation parameters is studied in Ref. [7] It is found that the Δm_{21}^2 and $\sin^2 \theta_{12}$ parameters will be determined to better than 0.5% precision in six years of data collection. In the same period, the Δm_{31}^2 parameter will be determined to about 0.2% precision for each mass ordering hypothesis. The new precision represents approximately an order of magnitude improvement over existing constraints for these three parameters. The precision versus the data taking time is shown in Fig. 4.

An improved analysis [8] shows the discovery potential of the Diffuse Supernova Neutrino Background (DSNB) is 3σ with 3 years data taking. The physics potential of detecting ^8B , ^7Be , pep and CNO solar neutrinos is exploited in Refs. [9, 10]. It is found that precision levels of

Figure 3: The NMO discriminator $\Delta\chi^2_{\min}$ as a function of JUNO and TAO data taking time for both normal (red) ordering and inverted (blue) ordering. The horizontal black dashed lines represent 3σ , 4σ , and 5σ significance. The solid lines are for the cases of full systematic uncertainties, and the dashed lines are for the statistical-only case.

Figure 4: Relative precision of the oscillation parameters as a function of JUNO data taking time. The markers and vertical lines stand for 100 days, 6 years, and 20 years of data taking. The horizontal gray dashed line stands for 1% relative precision. The green dotted and red dotted lines are on top of each other since the statistical-only precision is essentially identical for the Δm^2_{31} and Δm^2_{21} parameters.

5%, 8% and 20% for the ^8B , $\sin^2\theta_{12}$, and Δm^2_{21} can be reached, respectively. The current best measurement of ^7Be , pep and CNO solar neutrinos can be improved in JUNO.

4 Overview of Daya Bay, RENO and Double Chooz

Fig. 5 shows and compares the precisions of $\sin^2 2\theta_{13}$ from Daya Bay [3], RENO [4], Double Chooz [5]. The antineutrino signal is selected using neutron capture on gadolinium (nGd) or

capture on hydrogen (nH) signals. Daya Bay obtained the current best precision of $\sin^2 2\theta_{13}$ and could improve the precision with full data set analysis with nH signal.

Figure 5: The precisions of the $\sin^2 2\theta_{13}$ measurements from Daya Bay, RENO and Double Chooz using neutron capture on gadolinium (nGd) or capture on hydrogen (nH) signals. Figure is provided by Maxim Gonchar.

5 Summary

This proceedings focus on the latest progresses on the JUNO detector and physics. JUNO detector is expected to start data taking in 2025 and will determine NMO with 3σ significance and precisely measure θ_{12} , Δm_{32}^2 and Δm_{21}^2 at sub-percent level with 6 years data taking. Daya Bay obtained the current best precision of $\sin^2 2\theta_{13}$ providing an important input for the future neutrino oscillation experiments.

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